

Using the NIST CSF for a Rapid Security Assessment

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1. Preface

This paper was written in 2016 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20161124> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

An *Information Technology Security Assessment* is a set of methods, procedures, and documents to find vulnerabilities and risks in an organization and assure that adequate security controls are well managed. Does it mean that you can walk through a company, fill a questionnaire, and write something in a fancy form?

Not really. Assessing an object is basically an easy job: Execute a check-list and confirm if it's compliant or not. But what if the object is a complex organization and you don't have months of time?

Many tools exist to support the auditor in his job; my favorite, with an optimal balance between complexity and completeness, is the *NIST Cybersecurity Framework* [1], or NIST-CSF.

3. The NIST Cyber Security Framework

CSF was originally built to provide guidance of critical enterprises. However, the contents of the NIST CSF are applicable to any firm, business, and enterprise with an interest in its own *cybersecurity*.

The CSF includes *implementation tiers* that support a high-level measurement of organizational cybersecurity and create a view of security that is measurable and organized by risk.

The five *framework core functions* are explained below. These functions are not intended to form a serial path, or lead to a static desired end state. Rather, the functions can be performed concurrently and continuously to form an operational culture that addresses the dynamic cybersecurity risk.

The NIST CSF identifies underlying key Categories and Sub-categories for each Function, and maps them to Informative References

Function	Category
IDENTIFY (ID)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Asset Management (ID.AM)Business Environment (ID.BE)Governance (ID.GV)Risk Assessment (ID.RA)Risk Management Strategy (ID.RM)
PROTECT (PR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Access Control (PR.AC)Awareness and Training (PR.AT)Data Security (PR.DS)Information Protection Processes and Procedures (PR.IP)Maintenance (PR.MA)Protective Technology (PR.PT)
DETECT (DT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Anomalies and Events (DE.AE)Security Continuous Monitoring (DE.CM)Detection Processes (DE.DP)
RESPOND (RS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Response Planning (RS.RP)Communications (RS.CO)Analysis (RS.AN)Mitigation (RS.MI)Improvements (RS.IM)
RECOVERY (RC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Recovery Planning (RC.RP)Improvements (RC.IM)Communications (RC.CO)

Identify (ID) – Develop the organizational understanding to manage cybersecurity risk to systems, assets, data, and capabilities.

Protect (PR) – Develop and implement the appropriate safeguards to ensure delivery of critical infrastructure services.

Detect (DE) – Develop and implement the appropriate activities to identify the occurrence of a cybersecurity event.

Respond (RS) – Develop and implement the appropriate activities to take action regarding a detected cybersecurity event.

Recover (RC) – Develop and implement the appropriate activities to maintain plans for resilience and to restore any capabilities or services that were impaired due to a cybersecurity event.

Figure: The NIST Cybersecurity Framework

4. Rapid Security Assessment (RSA)

A *security assessment* is a long sequence of reading documents, decoding infrastructure and processes, identification of gap between the list of controls in place and those required by legal or technical standards, checking if the process are in place and well managed, checking if the systems are configured as documented, documenting the differences, and reporting them. Even the sampling check and documentation of a single server may take days.

In most case, however, for an identification of the problem areas it is not necessary to go deep since first meeting. It is useful to quickly check different aspects of the organization and, with experience, it is possible to drive the corrective action plan in an efficient manner. But, if you are quick, you are also prone to errors. During assessment you are normally finger-pointing at people and this may have consequences on those people, not always enjoyable.

The assessment must be rapid but also *complete and coherent*, and the results must be measurable.

We try to measure the quantity and the quality of the controls in place with following steps:

- **Collection:** Determine the cyber security exposure, prepare the on-site assessment, and review document. Interview the subject matter expert, review additional documents and, if necessary, inspect IT systems.
- **Analysis:** After completing the CAF matrix, they can calculate various performance parameters that help to interpret the situation and the direction to take. As the CSF is divided in functions and categories, so are the charts grouped.
- **Report:** The application of a security assessment to a cybersecurity control, in case of misalignment, produces assessment findings.

Figure: Rapid Security Assessment

5. Not Everyone Likes the Rainbow

Once a lot of information are collected, it is time to *analyze* them and *prioritize* problems. How to assign a G-Y-R code to each inspected control and measure the result? The NIST-CSF has a lot of controls, and not every organization has the resource to manage them.

We decided to set the absolute minimum at the *CIS Critical Security Controls* [2]. The CIS-CSC are a recommended set of actions for cyber defense that provide specific and actionable ways to stop today's most pervasive and dangerous attacks.

Mapping the CIS-CSC to NIST-CSF, makes possible to separate the performance of each control in the NIST-CSF in different areas:

- **Red area:** all below the minimum score of the CIS-CSC
- **Yellow area:** delimited by the minimum and the maximum score of the CIS-CSC

- **Green area:** all above the maximum scores of the CIS-CSC

Defined the metric, with some code and database relations, it is possible to get values/trends/performances from the data, and support our judgment with a more solid and understandable reason.

Here some examples of figures extracted:

Figure: RSA Analysis

6. Summary

A security assessment is a long sequence of actions that may take a lot of resource to produce results. Assessing a company is a complex and delicate problem, involving not only technical but also human aspects. We developed the *rapid security assessment* to produce fast and reliable results to help organizations to efficiently drive investments and efforts and to make the right tactic and strategic decision to improve they security posture.

7. External Links

- [1] <https://www.nist.gov/cyberframework>
- [2] <https://www.cisecurity.org/critical-controls.cfm>